

16th AgroStat Conference (AgroStat 2024):

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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September 3 – 6, 2024

Bragança, Portugal

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PREFACE

Dear Colleagues,

The AgroStat biannual series of conference are driven by the Agro-Industry Group of the French Statistical Society (SFdS), which is a non-profit organisation bringing together researchers, engineers, teachers and statistics users (<https://www.sfds.asso.fr>). The 16th Edition of the AgroStat Conference (AgroStat 2024) will take place from the 3th to 6th September 2024 in the city of Bragança, Portugal, hosted and organised by the Polytechnic Institute of Bragança (IPB).

Bragança is a typically-Portuguese old town (Romanic origin dates back to the 10th century), located by the Natural Park of Montesinho – one of the wildest forest zones of Europe – and the Douro Valley – the third oldest protected wine region in the world; and surrounded by traditional villages of a distinctive rustic beauty. Bragança houses several traditional industries producing a myriad of local foods, such as cheese, fermented meats, wine, chestnuts and honey, which provide substantial economic sustainability to the region.

The AgroStat 2024 conference will reunite internationally recognised researchers and industrial organisations representatives, to take stock of advances in statistics, express their needs and to anticipate future challenges. The AgroStat 2024 conference will provide engineers, modellers, statisticians, developers and end-users, a unique opportunity to exchange knowledge and prospects around novel statistical methods applied to agri-food and sensory sciences. We expect to gather a significant number of delegates to participate in a comprehensive scientific programme that includes 5 keynote lectures, and oral communications, allocated in sessions focusing on the following themes: Sensometrics, Chemometrics, Experimental designs, Process control, Risk analysis, Big Data and Software tools.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The IPB Chairs acknowledge that “Session 10: EU PRIMA Online Session” was funded by PRIMA project “*Productivity, Adaptiveness, Sustainability and Profitability of Agropastoral Systems in Mediterranean Countries*” (PAS-AGRO-PAS; PRIMA/0014/2022).

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Keywords: Anisakids; Europe; Fish; Contamination

CAPABILITY OF AUTOCHTHONOUS LACTIC ACID BACTERIA SUPERNATANT FROM DAIRY FOODS TO INHIBIT *SALMONELLA ENTERICA*: A META-REGRESSION STUDY

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This systematic review aimed to assess the antimicrobial activity of lactic acid bacteria (LAB) supernatant against *Salmonella* (*S.*) *enterica* serovar Typhimurium, a common contaminant of dairy products. A comprehensive search of PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science databases yielded 14 relevant studies, providing 100 observations.

Multilevel fixed-effects meta-analysis regressions were conducted to analyze mean inhibition diameters resulting from the supernatant of LAB and to explore the influence of moderators such as susceptibility method, agar medium, and incubation time on in vitro assay results. Using the 'metafor' package in R 4.1.2, meta-analysis models and graphs were constructed. The primary outcome measured was the mean inhibition zone diameter (ID) and its standard error (SE).

Results from the initial fixed model, employing a pathogen concentration of 7 log CFU/mL and an incubation time of 24 hours, indicated that *Lactococcus* (12.76 ± 1.194 mm) exhibited the highest inhibition values against *S. enterica*, followed by *Lactobacillus* (12.36 ± 1.148 mm) and *Enterococcus* (12.00 ± 1.195 mm). A second model considered the susceptibility method as a moderator, revealing that the well diffusion test yielded higher inhibition values compared to spot and disk diffusion tests ($p=0.009$). This discrepancy could be attributed to the superior diffusion of supernatant in the well test compared to the disk test, owing to mechanical perforation of the agar versus solely diffusion. The best-fit regression model for *S. enterica*, incorporating susceptibility method, agar medium and incubation time, explained 52.3% of the total variance. Notably, a positive and significant correlation between incubation time and inhibition values was observed ($p<0.001$), with longer incubation periods (e.g., 72 hours) resulting in higher inhibition values. The tendency of pH and inhibition diameter values had a significant effect ($p<0.001$), for instance, *Lactobacillus* displayed higher inhibitory activity at more acidic pH (ID=25 mm) compared to neutral pH (ID=15 mm).

Overall, the inhibition of *S. enterica* by *Lactobacillus* highlights the potential of probiotic lactobacilli in promoting gastrointestinal health and preventing foodborne illnesses.

Incorporating *Lactobacillus*-containing foods or probiotic supplements into the diet may enhance the natural defences against *Salmonella* and other pathogenic bacteria in the gut.

Keywords: Antimicrobial peptides; Hurdle technology; Cheese; Bacteriocinogenic

Session 4: Sensometrics I

Time: 14:50 - 15:50

Date: 4th September 2024

CATEGORICAL FUNCTIONAL DATA ANALYSIS APPLIED TO TEMPORAL DOMINANCE OF SENSATIONS DATA

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Sensory analysis is a multidisciplinary field aiming at describing sensory perception and appreciation of food and non-food products by consumers. It features several experimental protocols including temporal ones. Among them, Temporal Dominance of Sensations (TDS) involves subjects indicating the dominant sensation among a list of descriptors (the categorical states of the stochastic process) at each moment throughout the tasting of an intake of the product.

Categorical functional data analysis extends the traditional functional data analysis to temporal categorical data, making it particularly relevant for TDS data. CFDA is now supported by a R-package (CFDA). Applied to TDS data, it produces a PCA-like map of the sensory evaluations of the products by the subjects (the trajectories) based on the sequences of sensations perceived. Each axis represents leading temporal patterns and the coordinates of sensory evaluations on these axes depict their main temporal characteristics. Then, those coordinates can be used as inputs for further statistical analyses such as clustering of subjects or discriminant analysis of products, both based on temporal perception.

This paper shows the application of CFDA on both a pedagogical dataset and a TDS dataset wherein subjects were connected to a gustometer delivering controlled temporal stimuli in the mouth of the subjects. Additionally, it discusses further opportunities and challenges associated with the application of functional data analysis to different other kinds of sensory data